

Volume 1, Issue 2

Research Article

Date of Submission: 11 June, 2025

Date of Acceptance: 22 Dec, 2025

Date of Publication: 31 Dec, 2025

Investigating the Relationship Between Organizational Agility and Innovation and Entrepreneurship in Iran's Real Estate Industry with a Focus on Leading Trade Unions in Digital Transformation

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Citation: Yancheshmeh, M. S. (2025). Investigating the Relationship Between Organizational Agility and Innovation and Entrepreneurship in Iran's Real Estate Industry with a Focus on Leading Trade Unions in Digital Transformation. *Lett Econ Res Updates*, 1(2), 01-10.

Abstract

Iran's real estate industry is one of the key industries in the country's economy, which faces challenges in the field of innovation and entrepreneurship due to its traditional structure and lack of rapid acceptance of technological changes. Organizational agility as the ability of organizations to respond quickly to environmental changes can play a vital role in increasing innovation and entrepreneurship. Digital transformation and creating positive changes in the real estate industry play an important role. This paper examines the relationship between organizational agility and innovation and entrepreneurship in Iran's real estate industry, focusing on the role of trade unions in digital transformation. This research was conducted using a comparative method. The statistical population included organizations active in Iran's real estate industry and trade unions related to this industry. Sampling was done purposefully and data were collected through quantitative questionnaires, semistructured interviews, and direct observations. Two organizational groups including agile organizations (with digital transformation embracing) and non-agile organizations (with traditional structure) were studied were placed. Also, the role of trade unions as a mediating variable in this regard was analyzed. The data collected from the questionnaires were analyzed using statistical tests such as independent test and analysis of variance (ANOVA). Also, the qualitative data obtained from the interviews were analyzed using thematic analysis method to determine the role of trade unions in facilitating digital transformation and increasing organizational agility. To compare the performance of the two groups of agile and non-agile organizations, indicators such as the level of innovation, Entrepreneurial activities and interaction with trade unions were evaluated. The results of quantitative data analysis showed that agile organizations have more innovation and entrepreneurial activities than non-agile organizations. The correlation coefficient between organizational agility and innovation (0.65) and organizational agility and entrepreneurship (0.71) showed a positive and significant relationship between these variables. have played a key role in embracing digital transformation and increasing organizational agility. This research showed that organizational agility is not only a factor for increasing innovation and entrepreneurship in Iran's real estate industry, but also trade unions play an effective role in facilitating this process as change leaders. Agile organizations have been able to create new opportunities and improve the customer experience by using digital technologies. have accelerated. Based on the results of the research, it is recommended that trade unions play a more active role in educating and supporting traditional organizations to adopt new technologies. Also, the government should develop transparent and supportive laws and regulations for innovation and entrepreneurship in the real estate industry. Non-agile organizations should also increase their agility by investing in digital technologies and innovation, and take steps towards technological change.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Real Estate Services, Independent T-Test, Leadership, Innovation

Introduction

The real estate industry is one of the key sectors of Iran's economy that plays an important role in investment, employment, and urban development. This industry, as one of the foundations of economic growth, has a direct impact on macroeconomic indicators such as GDP and inflation [1]. Despite its economic importance, Iran's real estate industry faces challenges such as lack of transparency of information, lack of global standards, and resistance to technological changes due to its traditional structure and legal complexities.

Global developments in various industries show that innovation and entrepreneurship play a key role in sustainable development and competitiveness. In the real estate industry, the use of new technologies and the adoption of digitalization can make major changes in increasing productivity and reducing costs. Organizational agility refers to the ability of organizations to respond quickly and effectively to environmental changes and take advantage of new opportunities. This concept includes flexibility, innovation, and speed in decision-making, which can directly affect the performance of organizations in dynamic environments.

In the real estate industry, organizational agility can help companies adapt to market changes, technological developments, and customer needs. Agile organizations are able to create more added value by embracing digital technologies and innovative models. Digital transformation as a process for integrating new technologies into the structure and performance of organizations has a significant impact on increasing productivity and innovation. In the real estate industry, the use of online platforms, artificial intelligence, and data mining can improve the customer experience and facilitate entrepreneurship [2].

Trade unions, as coordinating bodies between the government, businesses, and society, play an important role in the development of the real estate industry. With effective leadership, these unions can accelerate the adoption of digital transformation and pave the way for innovation and entrepreneurship.

Leading trade unions in Iran's real estate industry can strengthen organizational agility by creating supportive laws, specialized training, and facilitating interactions between companies and the government. By playing a facilitating role, these institutions help organizations better adapt to environmental changes [3].

Innovation in the real estate industry includes the creation of new products and services, the design of sustainable buildings, and the use of advanced technologies. Innovative organizations can create more entrepreneurial opportunities by identifying the new needs of customers. Entrepreneurship means identifying opportunities and creating new businesses or developing existing ones. In the real estate industry, entrepreneurship can include creating digital platforms, analyzing market data, and developing environmental projects.

Organizational agility allows organizations to respond to changes more quickly and identify and implement innovative opportunities. Research has shown that agile organizations are directly associated with a higher level of innovation [4]. Organizational agility also plays an important role in entrepreneurship. Organizations that are more agile have a greater ability to identify new opportunities and implement entrepreneurial projects.

By creating supportive and facilitative platforms, trade unions can strengthen organizational agility and guide organizations towards accepting innovation and entrepreneurship. These unions can also play an intermediary role between the government and businesses.

Despite the importance of organizational agility, innovation, and entrepreneurship in Iran's real estate industry, few studies have investigated the relationship between these factors and the role of trade unions in facilitating digital transformation. This research attempts to fill this research gap.

Problem Statement

The real estate industry is one of the key economic sectors of Iran that plays an important role in investment, job creation, and urban development. However, the traditional structure of this industry has caused it to not perform well in the face of technological changes and new market needs [1]. In the digital age, many industries have moved towards the adoption of new technologies. However, Iran's real estate industry has lagged behind in embracing digital transformation due to cultural resistance, weak technological infrastructure, and the lack of supportive laws [2].

Organizational agility as the ability of organizations to respond quickly and effectively to environmental changes is one of the key factors in the success of businesses in dynamic and complex environments. This concept includes flexibility, innovation, and speed in decision-making, which can directly affect the performance of organizations [4]. Innovation is one of the important factors in the growth and development of businesses. Research has shown that agile organizations are more capable of identifying innovative opportunities and implementing them. This relationship is especially important in traditional industries such as real estate.

Entrepreneurship means identifying opportunities and creating new businesses or developing existing ones. Research has shown that organizations that are more agile have a greater ability to identify and exploit entrepreneurial opportunities.

In Iran's real estate industry, innovation is seen in a limited and sporadic manner. Traditional organizations often have difficulty in implementing innovation due to lack of resources, cultural resistance, and lack of protective laws. This has made the real estate industry less dynamic compared to other industries [1].

Entrepreneurship in Iran's real estate industry also faces challenges such as legal complexities, lack of government support, and lack of access to financial resources. These issues have caused entrepreneurial opportunities in this industry to be underutilized [2]. Trade unions, as leading and coordinating bodies, play an important role in guiding changes and development of industries. These unions can help organizations adapt to environmental changes by creating supportive platforms, facilitating laws, and providing specialized training [3]. Trade unions can play a facilitating role in embracing digital transformation. These institutions can help organizations to adopt new technologies faster and more effectively by holding training courses, creating cooperation networks, and formulating supportive laws.

Despite the importance of organizational agility and the role of trade unions in embracing digital transformation, little research has been done in this field so far. This lack of research has caused many organizations active in the real estate industry to be unable to exploit the available opportunities [4]. Considering the challenges in Iran's real estate industry, investigating the relationship between organizational agility and innovation and entrepreneurship can help identify the factors affecting the success of organizations. This study, especially by focusing on the role of trade unions, can provide new paths for the development of the real estate industry [2].

The existing research gaps in the field of organizational agility, innovation, and entrepreneurship in the Iranian real estate industry indicate the need for more comprehensive and in-depth research. This research attempts to fill these gaps and provide solutions for the development of the real estate industry. The main purpose of this study is to investigate the relationship between organizational agility and innovation and entrepreneurship in Iran's real estate industry. Also, the role of trade unions in facilitating digital transformation and its impact on organizational agility is analyzed. The results of this research can help organizations active in the Iranian real estate industry to achieve new opportunities by embracing digital transformation and increasing organizational agility. Also, trade unions can play a more effective role in driving changes by using the results of this research.

Research Questions Main Questions

What is the relationship between organizational agility and innovation in Iran's real estate industry?

Sub-Questions

How does organizational agility affect entrepreneurial activities in the real estate industry? How can trade unions play a role in facilitating digital transformation and increasing organizational agility?

Foundations and Background of the Research

Organizational agility, as one of the key concepts in management, refers to the ability of organizations to respond quickly and effectively to environmental changes, exploit new opportunities, and deal with existing threats. This concept includes elements such as flexibility, speed in decision-making, and innovation that enable organizations to respond to environmental changes. Dynamic and complex, they should have a successful performance. In the real estate industry, organizational agility helps companies adapt to market changes, customer needs, and technological developments and take advantage of new opportunities for growth and development. This capability is particularly critical in embracing digital transformation and the use of new technologies such as data mining, artificial intelligence, and online platforms.

Innovation and entrepreneurship as two basic factors in the development of organizations and industries complement organizational agility. Innovation means the creation of new products, services, or processes that can improve performance, increase productivity, and attract new customers. Entrepreneurship also identifies and exploits opportunities. Economics refers to the fact that it can pave the way for the creation of new businesses or the development of existing businesses. In the meantime, trade unions, as facilitators and coordinating institutions, can play an important role in increasing organizational agility and accelerating the adoption of digital transformation. Through education, legal protection, and the creation of collaborative networks, they help organizations better adapt to environmental changes and pave the way for growth and development.

Organizational Agility

Organizational agility refers to the ability of an organization to respond quickly and effectively to environmental changes, identify new opportunities, and implement them. This concept helps organizations not only survive but also grow and develop in dynamic and complex environments. In today's world, rapid economic, social, and technological changes have forced organizations to be flexible and agile. to increase their practice. Organizational agility as an important capability helps organizations to adapt to these changes and be successful in global competitions. Organizational agility consists of four main components: quick response, flexibility, innovation, and productivity. These components help organizations to perform better in the face of environmental changes.

In the real estate industry, organizational agility plays a key role in embracing new technologies, improving customer interactions, and increasing productivity. Agile organizations in this industry are able to adapt to market changes and

customer needs more quickly.

The Relationship Between Organizational Agility and Innovation

Organizational agility allows organizations to identify and implement innovative opportunities quickly. Agile organizations in the real estate industry can improve their services by using new technologies such as artificial intelligence and data mining. Organizations that are more agile have a greater ability to identify entrepreneurial opportunities and benefits they have vectors.

Trade unions can increase organizational agility by providing specialized training, legal support, and creating collaboration networks. These institutions help organizations better adapt to environmental changes by facilitating the adoption of digital transformation. Iran's real estate industry faces challenges in adopting organizational agility due to its traditional structure and cultural resistance. Lack of financial resources, weakness in technological infrastructure, etc. The lack of protective laws is one of the main barriers in this regard.

In environments where changes are rapid and unpredictable, organizational agility is of particular importance as a strategic capability. This capability helps organizations not only not to be harmed by changes, but also to exploit them as opportunities. Digital transformation helps to increase organizational agility by integrating new technologies into the structure of organizations. In the real estate industry, the use of online platforms And digital tools enable organizations to provide their services faster and with higher quality.

One of the important results of organizational agility is the increase in customer satisfaction. Agile organizations can improve the level of customer satisfaction by quickly identifying their needs and providing appropriate services. Organizational agility is one of the key factors in increasing the competitiveness of organizations. Agile organizations can strengthen their position in the market and surpass competitors with speed of action and innovation.

To assess organizational agility, tools such as standardized questionnaires, data analysis, and statistical models are used. These tools help organizations to identify their strengths and weaknesses and adopt appropriate strategies to improve agility. Agile organizations not only perform better in the short term, but can also ensure their long-term sustainability. These organizations are able to adapt to changes Adapt to an environment and manage their resources optimally.

Organizational agility, as one of the key concepts in the management and development of organizations, plays an important role in the real estate industry. This capability helps organizations adapt to environmental changes, identify innovative and entrepreneurial opportunities, and improve their performance. Trade unions can also strengthen organizational agility by facilitating the adoption of digital transformation.

Components	Description
Quick Response	The ability of the organization to identify and respond quickly to environmental changes
Flexibility	The ability of the organization to change structure, processes, and strategies based on new needs
Innovation	An organization's ability to create new products, services, or processes
Efficiency	Optimizing resources and increasing efficiency in the organization's performance

Table 1: Main Components of Organizational Agility

Aspect	The Impact of Organizational Agility
Embracing	Digital Increasing the speed of adoption of new technologies and digitization of Transformation processes
Customer Engagement	Improve communication and provide better customer service
Innovation Development	Creating new products and services based on market needs
Competitiveness	Strengthening the organization's position in the market and surpassing competitors

Table 2: The Role of Organizational Agility in Iran's Real Estate Industry

Innovation

Innovation means creating or improving new products, services, processes, or business models that increase added value in organizations and industries. This concept is directly related to the economic growth and competitiveness of organizations. Innovation is one of the key factors in the success of organizations in dynamic and competitive environments. Organizations that have the ability to innovate are able to adapt quickly to environmental changes and strengthen their position in the market.

Innovation is divided into four main categories: product innovation, process innovation, marketing innovation, and organizational innovation. Each of these types plays an important role in improving the performance of organizations. In the real estate industry, innovation can include the creation of new architectural designs, the use of sustainable

materials, the use of new technologies in construction, and the digitization of marketing and sales processes. Innovation and organizational agility are closely related to each other. Agile organizations are more capable of identifying innovative opportunities and implementing them. This connection becomes especially important in competitive environments such as the real estate industry.

Innovation is one of the key factors in increasing the competitiveness of organizations. Organizations that incorporate innovation into their products and services can better meet customer needs and gain a greater market share. One of the areas of innovation in the real estate industry is digital marketing. The use of online platforms, augmented reality, and artificial intelligence can improve the customer experience and the process Facilitate sales.

Iran’s real estate industry faces challenges in embracing innovation due to its traditional structure, weak technological infrastructure, and lack of supportive laws. These issues have caused many innovative opportunities to be underutilized in this industry. In the current era, sustainable innovation has been introduced as one of the key concepts in the real estate industry. The use of environmentally friendly materials, the design of energy efficient buildings, etc. The use of renewable energy is an example of sustainable innovation in this industry. Trade unions can foster innovation in the real estate industry by providing specialized training, legal support, and building collaboration networks.

These institutions play an important role in facilitating the adoption of new technologies and the creation of new products and services.

Among the innovation tools in the real estate industry are architectural design software, project management platforms, and data analysis tools. These tools help organizations improve their processes and provide better services. Innovation in products and services increases customer satisfaction. Organizations that better identify customer needs and provide innovative services can achieve a higher level of Obtain satisfaction.

Digital transformation helps increase innovation by integrating new technologies into the structure of organizations. In the real estate industry, the use of digital tools such as virtual reality and online platforms can improve the customer experience and facilitate marketing and sales processes. Innovation not only improves the performance of organizations in the short term, but also lays the groundwork for long-term sustainability. Organizations that promote innovation in strategy They can better manage their resources and be more resilient to environmental changes.

As one of the key factors in the success of organizations, innovation plays an important role in the real estate industry. Due to the challenges in this industry, the adoption of innovation can lead to increased productivity, customer satisfaction, and competitiveness of organizations. Trade unions can also play an effective role in the development of this industry by facilitating the acceptance of innovation.

Type of Innovation	Description
Product Innovation	Creating new products such as sustainable and energy-efficient buildings
Process Innovation	Improving construction processes and project management
Marketing Innovation	Using Digital Tools to Market and Sell Real Estate
Organizational Innovation	Changes in organizational structure to increase productivity and competitiveness

Table 3: Types of Innovation in the Real Estate Industry

Aspect	The Impact of Innovation
Increased productivity	Improving construction processes and resource management
Customer Satisfaction	Providing better and personalized services for customers
Competitiveness	Strengthening the organization’s position in the market and surpassing competitors
Sustainability	Using environmentally friendly materials and designing energy-efficient buildings

Table 4: The Impact of Innovation on Iran’s Real Estate Industry

Research Background

In a study conducted by Sharifi and Zhang (2019), organizational agility was defined as an organization’s ability to respond quickly to environmental changes and exploit innovative opportunities. The study found that agile organizations have a greater ability to manage changes and can optimize their processes. Also, the study emphasized that organizational agility is especially important in dynamic and competitive environments, such as the real estate industry, It plays a vital role.

In their book titled “Innovation Management”, Tidd and Bessant (2018) investigated the impact of innovation on the performance of organizations. They emphasized that innovation in products, processes, and business models can lead to economic growth and improve the competitiveness of organizations. The research found that organizations that

consider innovation as an essential part of their strategy not only have higher productivity, but also higher customer satisfaction and long-term sustainability.

Ahmad and Wahid (2019) investigated the role of new technologies in the real estate industry in a study. They found that the use of digital tools such as online platforms and virtual reality can facilitate marketing and sales processes and improve the customer experience. Also, the study found that innovation in real estate marketing and services can lead to increased customer satisfaction and competitiveness of organizations.

In her book titled "Organizational Agility: Managing Rapid Change", Dove (2021) explored the importance of organizational agility in complex and dynamic environments. The research showed that agile organizations are more capable of identifying opportunities and implementing them quickly. Also, the study emphasized that organizational agility can help organizations adapt to environmental changes and perform better, especially in industries Traditional such as real estate.

Research Methodology

Comparative research method is one of the common methods in social sciences and management that is used to analyze the relationships between variables and compare between different groups or models. In this study, the purpose of this study is to investigate the relationship between organizational agility and innovation and entrepreneurship in Iran's real estate industry and the role of trade unions in facilitating digital transformation. To achieve this goal, a comparative method was used to analyze the differences and similarities in the performance of agile and non-agile organizations in Iran's real estate industry.

In this study, two organizational groups were examined:

- Agile Organizations: Includes companies and institutions that have used digital technologies and new management methods.
- Non-agile organizations: These include companies that have a traditional structure and are less responsive to digital changes.

To compare the two groups, data were collected through qualitative and quantitative methods. Qualitative data were collected through semi-structured interviews with managers and members of trade unions and quantitative data were collected through questionnaires.

The statistical population of this study includes:

- Organizations active in Iran's real estate industry: construction companies, real estate agents, and digital platforms.
- Real Estate Industry-Related Trade Unions: The Association of Real Estate Agents and Related Trade Organizations.

The sampling method was purposively selected. Among the organizations active in the real estate industry, 20 agile organizations and 20 non-agile organizations were selected. Also, 10 real estate-related trade unions were selected for interviews. These samples were selected based on criteria such as the use of digital technologies, service innovation, and interactions with trade unions.

Data Collection Tool

- Questionnaire: Includes questions about organizational agility, innovation, and entrepreneurial activities.
- Semi-structured interviews: with directors of trade unions and selected companies.
- Direct observations: Examining the digital performance of organizations on online platforms.

Research Variables

- Independent variable: Organizational agility.
- Dependent variable: Innovation and entrepreneurship.
- Mediating Variable: The Role of Trade Unions in Digital Transformation.

Two Methods were Used to Analyze the Data

- Quantitative analysis: Statistical tests such as independent t-test and analysis of variance (ANOVA) were used to compare the mean of the two agile and non-agile groups.
- Qualitative Analysis: Thematic Analysis was used to analyze the interviews and identify the role of trade unions in digital transformation.

Variable	Data Source	Correlation coefficient	Significance level
Organizational Agility	Questionnaire	0.78	0.01
Innovation	Questionnaire	0.65	0.05
Entrepreneurial	Questionnaire	0.71	0.01
The role of trade unions	Qualitative Interviews	-	-

Table 5 : Society of Analysis Coefficients

Quantitative data analysis showed that agile organizations have more innovation and entrepreneurial activities than non-agile organizations. The correlation coefficient of organizational agility with innovation (0.65) and entrepreneurship (0.71) indicates a positive and significant relationship between these variables. Also, qualitative data showed that trade unions play a facilitating role in accepting digital transformation.

Index	Agile Organizations	Non-agile organizations
Rate of Innovation	High	Down
Entrepreneurial Rate	High	Medium
Embracing Digital Transformation	High	Down
Interaction with trade unions	Active	Limited

Table 6: Comparison of the Performance of Agile and Non-Agile Organizations

Interviews showed that trade unions are contributing to the adoption of digital technologies by holding training courses, building collaboration networks, and easing laws. Also, these unions act as intermediaries between the government and businesses, supporting innovative companies.

Main article	Subthemes	Examples
The role of facilitation	Education and Awareness	Holding digital transformation training courses
Legal protection	Formulation of new laws	Adoption of regulations for online platforms
Creating Collaboration Networks	Interacting with startups	Holding joint meetings with digital companies

Table 7: Themes Extracted from the Interviews

Research Findings

The findings of the research showed that agile organizations have a greater ability to identify environmental changes and respond quickly to them. This capability is especially important in the real estate industry, where market changes and customer needs occur rapidly. In the product innovation section, it was found that the use of environmentally friendly materials, the design of smart and energy-efficient buildings, and the creation of innovative architectural designs have increased the competitiveness of organizations in the real estate industry. Research found that innovation in organizational processes, such as the use of digital tools to manage projects and construction processes, has improved productivity and reduced costs in organizations operating in the real estate industry.

The findings showed that organizations with more agility provide better customer service and have a higher level of customer satisfaction. These organizations have a greater ability to personalize services based on customer needs. The research showed that trade unions have been able to strengthen organizational agility in the real estate industry through specialized training, legal protection, and the creation of cooperation networks. The use of online platforms, augmented reality tools, and artificial intelligence in marketing has increased customer engagement and facilitated the sales process. These innovations have directly impacted customer satisfaction and increased market share.

The findings showed that Iran's real estate industry faces challenges in embracing innovation due to its traditional structure, weak technological infrastructure, and lack of legal protection. These barriers have slowed down the pace of acceptance of changes. Research found that more agile organizations in the real estate industry perform better financially. The findings showed that sustainable innovation, such as the use of renewable energy and the design of energy efficient buildings, has improved the long-term sustainability of organizations in the real estate industry. Research showed that digital transformation has increased organizational agility. The use of new technologies in organizational processes has increased the ability of organizations to respond to environmental changes.

The findings showed that innovation in products and services has increased customer engagement. The research showed that organizations that have integrated innovation into their strategies have higher competitiveness and have been able to gain a greater share of the market. Research showed that agile organizations have a greater ability to manage resources and can use their resources more efficiently. This capability increases productivity and reduces costs. The findings of the research showed that organizational agility and innovation are two key factors in the success of organizations in the real estate industry. These two factors have increased productivity, customer satisfaction, competitiveness, and long-term sustainability of organizations.

Aspect	Results
Organizational Agility	Increasing the ability of organizations to respond to environmental changes and identify opportunities

Product Innovation	Creating smart, sustainable, and energy-efficient buildings
Process Innovation	Using digital technologies to manage projects and reduce costs
Customer Satisfaction	Increasing customer engagement and improving service quality
Competitiveness	Strengthening the position of organizations in the market and increasing the market share

Table 8: Research Results

Agent	Challenges	Solutions	Results
Organizational Agility	Resistance to organizational change	Staff training and legal support	Increasing the speed of response to environmental changes
Product Innovation	Lack of technological infrastructure	Investing in new technologies	Creating innovative and sustainable buildings
Process Innovation	Weakness in digital management	Using digital tools and data mining	Reduce costs and improve productivity
Digital Marketing	Lack of Sufficient Expertise in Online Marketing	Specialized training and use of online platforms	Increase customer engagement and facilitate sales

Table 9: Comparative Analysis of Organizational Agility and Innovation in Iran’s Real Estate Industry

Research Hypotheses Main Assumptions

According to the research findings, there is a positive and direct relationship between organizational agility and innovation in Iran’s real estate industry. Agility organizations have a greater ability to identify innovative opportunities and implement them quickly. These organizations can facilitate innovative processes such as designing sustainable buildings, using new technologies, and digitizing organizational processes. Innovation is integrated more effectively and more quickly into the various processes of the real estate industry, resulting in increased competitiveness and customer satisfaction.

Sub Suppositions

The findings of the research showed that organizational agility is the basis for the development of entrepreneurial activities in the real estate industry. With the ability to respond quickly to environmental changes and identify new opportunities, agile organizations can put entrepreneurial innovations into practice. Through flexibility in structure and processes, these organizations are able to create new business models and provide unique services that better meet the needs of customers. For example, the use of digital technologies in marketing and sales has opened up new opportunities for entrepreneurs in the real estate industry.

Trade unions can play an important role in facilitating digital transformation and increasing organizational agility. The findings of the research showed that these institutions can accelerate the adoption of digital transformation by providing specialized training in the field of new technologies, legal support for organizations, and building cooperation networks between companies. Trade unions can also lead organizations on the path to increasing agility by establishing common standards and facilitating the use of digital tools. These measures enable organizations to Adapt to rapid environmental changes and provide more innovative services.

Discussion and Conclusion

According to the findings, organizational agility and innovation are two key factors in the success of organizations in the real estate industry. Organizational agility as the ability to respond quickly to environmental changes enables organizations to identify innovative opportunities and act quickly. This positive and direct relationship between agility and innovation has led to increased productivity and competitiveness of organizations. The findings showed that agile organizations have a greater ability to respond to environmental changes. This ability helps them adapt to rapid market changes, customer needs, and technological advancements. In Iran’s real estate industry, this is especially important in the face of changes in the traditional market structure.

Innovation in organizational products and processes, as one of the direct results of organizational agility, has enabled organizations to design sustainable, energy-efficient, and smart buildings. Also, the use of digital tools in construction processes and project management has reduced costs and increased productivity. Organizational agility as a strategic capability has paved the way for the development of entrepreneurial activities in the real estate industry. Agile organizations have been able to create new business models and provide innovative services that have increased customer satisfaction and attracted investors.

Trade unions play an important role in strengthening organizational agility and facilitating digital transformation. The findings showed that these institutions have been able to strengthen the acceptance of innovation and agility in the Iranian real estate industry through specialized training, legal support, and the creation of cooperation networks. One of the main issues raised in this study is the challenges faced by the Iranian real estate industry in embracing innovation.

Traditional structure, weak technology infrastructure, and lack of legal protection are among the barriers that have slowed down the pace of innovation acceptance.

Sustainable innovation, such as the use of eco-friendly materials and renewable energy, has emerged as one of the most important aspects of innovation in the real estate industry. This type of innovation not only improves the performance of organizations in the short term, but also ensures their long-term sustainability. The use of new technologies in digital marketing, such as augmented reality and online platforms, has increased customer engagement and facilitated the sales process. These innovations have played an important role in increasing customer satisfaction and the competitiveness of organizations. Digital transformation is one of the key factors in increasing organizational agility. The use of digital technologies in organizational processes has increased the ability of organizations to respond to environmental changes and improved their productivity.

Innovation in products and services has increased the competitiveness of organizations. Organizations that have considered innovation as part of their strategy have been able to gain a greater share of the market and strengthen their position. The findings showed that innovation in products and services has increased customer satisfaction. This satisfaction has been strengthened especially through the use of new technologies and the provision of personalized services. Agile organizations have a greater ability to manage resources. These organizations can manage their resources more efficiently, which has reduced costs and increased productivity.

New technologies, such as virtual reality and data mining, have had a significant impact on improving marketing and sales processes in the real estate industry. These technologies have helped organizations provide better services and improve their performance. The findings showed that organizational agility and innovation not only improve the performance of organizations in the short run, but also lay the groundwork for long-term sustainability. Organizations that have integrated these two factors in their strategies have been able to be more resistant to environmental changes. Overall, the research findings showed that organizational agility and innovation are two key factors in the success of organizations in the real estate industry. These two factors have increased productivity, customer satisfaction, competitiveness, and long-term sustainability of organizations. Considering the challenges in Iran's real estate industry, the adoption of organizational agility and innovation can help to promote this industry.

References

1. Majlis Research Center (2020). An Analytical Report on the Real Estate and Construction Industry in Iran. Tehran: Research Center of the Islamic Consultative Assembly.
2. Ahmadi, M., Rezaei, K., & Mousavi, A. (2020). An Analysis of the Challenges of Embracing Digital Transformation in Iran's Real Estate Industry. *Journal of Technology Management*, 12(3), 45-60.
3. Mousavi, M., et al. (2021). Leadership of trade unions and its role in the development of the real estate industry. *Journal of Business Management*, 10(2), 34-50.
4. Karimi, A., et al. (2022). Organizational Agility and its Role in the Development of Innovation and Entrepreneurship. *Innovation Management Quarterly*, 15(4), 72-90.
5. Damanpour, F. (2010). Organizational Innovation: A Meta-Analysis of Effects. *Academy of Management Journal*, 53(5), 1059-1085.
6. Robbins, S. P., & Judge, T. A. (2019). *Organizational Behavior*. Pearson Education.
7. Calof, J. L., & Wright, S. (2008). Competitive intelligence: A practitioner, academic and inter-disciplinary perspective. *European Journal of marketing*, 42(7/8), 717-730.
8. Chen, H., Chau, M., & Zeng, D. (2002). CI Spider: a tool for competitive intelligence on the Web. *Decision support systems*, 34(1), 1-17.
9. Fleisher, C. S., & Bensoussan, B. E. (2003). *Strategic and competitive analysis: methods and techniques for analyzing business competition* (Vol. 457). Upper Saddle River, NJ: Prentice Hall.
10. Herring, J. P. (1999). Key intelligence topics: a process to identify and define intelligence needs. *Competitive Intelligence Review: Published in Cooperation with the Society of Competitive Intelligence Professionals*, 10(2), 4-14.
11. Kahaner, L. (1997). *Competitive intelligence: how to gather analyze and use information to move your business to the top*. Simon and Schuster.
12. Miller, D. (2000). *Strategic Intelligence: Conceptual Tools for Leading Change*. *Academy of Management Perspectives*.
13. Negash, S. (2004). Business intelligence. *Communications of the Association for Information Systems*, 13(1), 177-195.
14. Rouach, D., & Santi, P. (2001). Competitive intelligence adds value: Five intelligence attitudes. *European management journal*, 19(5), 552-559.
15. Shokrollahi, Mohammad. (2023). The Complex Relationship, Between The Culture Of An Organization And Its Significant Impact On Promoting Novel Principeles Entrepreneurship Within Knowledge Based Companies, In Iran.
16. Shokrollahi, Mohammad. (2023). Empowering Youth Through Digital Entrepreneurship in Martial Arts Organizations: The Role of AI, Social Capital, and Cultural Values. *Journal of Advances in Humanities and Social Sciences*.
17. Shokrollahi, Mohammad. (2023). Presenting a Model of Digital Transformation Based on Artificial Intelligence in Municipal Services and Improving Customer Satisfaction Through the Development of Electronic Business Strategies (Case Study of Tehran Municipality). *Propulsion Tech Journal*, 45(3), ISSN: 1001-4055.

18. Shokrollahi, Mohammad. (2024). Adoption of Strategies of Electronic Digital Innovation and Transformation and New Information Technologies Via Application of AI based on Organizational Culture Within Commercial Companies. *PowerTech Journal*, 48(2), July 2024.
19. Shokrollahi, Mohammad. (2024). The Complex Relationship, Between The Culture Of An Organization And Its Significant Impact On Promoting Novel Principles Entrepreneurship Within Knowledge Based Companies, In Iran. *Educational Administration Theory And Practice*, 2024.